

FIBER OPTIC SENSORS FOR STRAIN MONITORING IN CONCRETE BEAMS REPAIRED WITH COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: Advanced composites offer some advantages over traditional procedures for repairing concrete structures, due to their optimal corrosion properties, low weight and decreasing costs. Thin cured laminates may be externally bonded or dry fabrics can be wet applied and in situ cured over the concrete structure, conforming to its surface irregularities.

Fibre optic strain sensors, specially Bragg gratings, show some advantages when compared to conventional strain gauges: absolute measurements, spectrally encoded output, no EMI, no drift (long-term stability), low size, multiplexing capability and their ability to be embedded into laminates without degradation.

The combination of both techniques is easy and offers important advantages. The long-term mechanical behaviour of the repair may be checked and information on environmental degradation could be obtained. On the short term, information on the stress transfer from the concrete to the laminate is obtained, and the validity of models is verified. Tests on a concrete beam repaired with CFRP and instrumented with Bragg gratings are reported. A finite element model was also developed.

KEYWORDS: repair, concrete, CFRP, fibre optic sensor, Bragg grating

1. INTRODUCTION

CFRP sheets externally bonded to concrete structures can replace metal sheets in repairs. The advantages of such a kind of arrangement are: ease of installation, light weight, high performances and flexibility. Some examples have been reported. One of them is the repair of the flat roof of an old building in La Spezia, Italy [1]. Another one is the strengthening of heat damaged pre-stressed concrete elements [2]. This technology is developing quickly and some kind of measurements may be needed in order to assure that the repair is working adequately.

Fiber optic sensors are starting to be widely used for in-service monitoring of high responsibility structures by measuring strain or deformation fields. Several arrangements are currently available: Fabry-Perot interferometers, Bragg gratings, interferometers (such as

Mach-Zender, Michelson, white-light, etc). Bragg gratings are probably the most promising kind, since they provide absolute measurements with excellent long-term stability due to their spectrally encoded output. Other advantages are the low size of this sensor (10 mm long, 125 μm diameter) which makes possible embedding them in laminates without impairing their mechanical properties, the use of a single optical fiber as information path and sensor host (all-fiber device), multiplexing capability (a few sensors can be placed in the same optical fiber), and no electromagnetic interference (EMI).

The use of Bragg gratings to measure the strain field in a CFRP repair in a concrete structure can be used, on the short term, to check the integrity of the repair, the load transfer from the concrete to the reinforcing patch and the validity of the models. On the long term it can be used to monitor the behaviour of the repair and its degradation.

To verify this concept, and to identify unforeseen issues, a concrete beam, previously damaged, was repaired using a thin CFRP patch; Bragg grating sensors were placed on top of it and at the concrete-composite patch interface, in order to measure the stress transfer. Conventional strain gauges and LVDTs were also placed on the beam to compare the measurements obtained with the optical sensors to those obtained by means of conventional technology. A finite element model for the repaired beam was developed [11,12] and experimental results were compared to those obtained from the model.

2. BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

Bragg gratings are optical fiber devices that provide information on the strain field along its sensor length. They consist on a periodic variation of the refractive index in the core of the fiber. When illuminated by a broadband light source, they reflect a narrow band, whose wavelength peak is given by the Bragg condition:

$$\lambda_B = 2nA$$

where n is the effective refractive index of the core and A is the modulation period. Any change in the length of the grating will shift the peak wavelength. Strain information is obtained through the measurement of this wavelength.

Some methods are currently available to determine the peak wavelength. The Optical Spectrum Analyzer can be replaced by the use of a scanning filter, taking advantage of a faster measurement rate, and using a less expensive device.

Our group at the University of Madrid has been working for the last 4 years on this technology [3-10]. Besides a facility for manufacturing Bragg gratings, we have developed our own demodulation equipment based on a tunable Fabry-Perot filter, that allow fast strain measurements (up to 50 Hz) and enough accuracy (30 $\mu\epsilon$). The schematic is shown in Figure 1. Light from an LED is launched into the optical fiber and a fraction of it is back reflected at the grating. It goes through a narrow band tunable filter and to the photoreceiver. Maximum voltage output is achieved when the filter and the grating are tuned, and peak wavelength is measured this way. Different gratings can be located in the same fiber as long as their peak wavelengths do not interfere.

Figure 1. Bragg gratings demodulation arrangement.

3. REPAIR EXECUTION

A reinforced concrete continuous beam with two spans (14.4 m long x 0.6 m wide), representative of current in-service civil engineering structures, was loaded up to failure and repaired in the Structures Laboratory of the Construction Engineering Department at UPC in Barcelona. This is part of a research experimental program looking at the feasibility and behaviour of concrete structures repaired with external prestressing and composite sheets and fabrics [14-16]. The composite repaired specimens are of the largest ever tested in a Laboratory. Therefore, they provide useful information regarding the behaviour of such repairs in full-scale structures. The target of this set of tests was the calculation of the ultimate stress in the original and repaired beam (with external prestressing) through measurements in a bending configuration. Loading arrangement is sketched in Fig. 2 aiming to achieve maximum bending at the central support: $2Q$ load was applied at the centre of one of the half-beam and two Q loads were applied at 2.4 m from supports in the other half-beam.

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Figure 2. Load application to achieve maximum bending at the central support.

The maximum load supported by the original structure was 92.8 kN. Extensive damage was produced at the middle of the beam with cracks that started from the tensile surface, crossing the steel reinforcing bars. In order to repair the structure, permanent deflection was cancelled

Figure 3. *Photograph of the repaired beam, showing the load application arrangement and the optical and electric cables.*

Figure 4. *Composite patch after failure at the upper central area of the concrete beam. Yellow cables are reinforced coated optical fibres.*

by means of several hydraulic jacks; damaged concrete near the cracks was subsequently removed and epoxy resin was injected in the flaws. Repairing non-retractile micro-concrete was poured in the cracks.

Beam surface near the cracks was mechanically prepared to get good enough adherence. Composite patches, made of two layers of carbon fabric, in-situ impregnated with room temperature epoxy resin, were extended over the crack locations, to transmit the load from the discontinued steel bars. Fiber optic strain sensors were placed with the fabrics, both in the internal and external surfaces. The repairing patches and Bragg gratings locations are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Bragg grating locations.

Besides the Bragg grating sensors, conventional resistive strain gauges in concrete, reinforcing steel, and composite patch surface, and LVDTs were added to acquire complete information on strain and deformation all over the structure.

4. TEST RESULTS

Load was applied in 4.5 kN steps. Flaws were visible from 145 kN on. Cracks began at the negative bending area and collapse happened suddenly when composite reinforcement reached its maximum strength. Some influence from the rotation around the central crack was also found: load transfer in the composite sheet was increasingly off-axis. Maximum load was 156.6 kN. This limit is higher than the original one (92.8 kN).

Strain vs. Load is plotted in Figure 6, obtained with strain gauges and FOS. Coincidence is very satisfactory, even at the non-linear region of the concrete beam. Visible non-linearity starts near 80 kN, still with considerable residual strength. Differences between strain gauges and Bragg gratings are due to the creep of the structure (measurements were made at same load but different times).

Results for Bragg grating sensors A and B are shown in Figure 7. They were at the same position, at one side and the other of the composite patch. A shear lag due to the finite thickness of the adhesive layer can be seen. The strain measured by sensor A, located in the interface, is higher than that measured by sensor B, at the same location but on top of the composite patch. This behaviour should be expected, as an adhesive joint, but has never been experimentally demonstrated previously.

Figure 6. Strain measurements (FOS and strain gauges)

Figure 7. Bragg grating measurements

5. MODELLING OF THE REPAIR

In order to justify the measurements, a very simple finite-element model of the repaired beam, using beam-elements, was developed. The strain fields in the patch and in the interface were calculated. Theoretical strain at the interface and at the top surface of the patch show a characteristic lag near the ends, as measured by fibre optic sensors. Shear strain has the classical hyperbolic distribution. A simple model was needed, not an exact model of the actual beam, but one able to give the trends in the strain in such a repair, since the non-linearity of the concrete, the anisotropic features of the composite materials and the complex geometry of the beam made it extremely difficult to model the real arrangement. This model will allow to optimise the design of the repair.

A two-dimensional beam model was selected; the element has previously been used to model active constrained layer damping [3]. The element consists of three components: the base beam, the adhesive layer and the composite layer. Each of these layers was assumed to have isotropic features. This assumption is valid for the concrete and the adhesive layer and not bad for the composite layer, using its equivalent longitudinal stiffness.

The model is based on the following assumptions:

1. The concrete beam is elastic and the transverse shear strain is negligible. The lateral displacement of the middle of the concrete beam, w , is shared by all points in the cross section. The longitudinal displacement of the base beam is not required to be zero (bending extension coupling is included) and the transverse and rotatory inertia are also included.
2. The adhesive layer has an additional shear angle associated with non-negligible transverse shear. Longitudinal normal strain in the adhesive layer is included as well as transverse and rotatory inertia.
3. The composite layer is isotropic, and the mean values of its longitudinal features are used. The rotations of the composite layer cross-sections are the same as the rotations of the base beam at the same x co-ordinate. The layer has both extensional and bending stiffness. Transverse and rotatory inertia are included.

Figure 8 shows the nodal degrees of freedom (DOF) of the element with length L . Further details are given in [3].

Figure 8. Degrees of freedom for the beam element with the composite patch on top.

6. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The dotted line (Fig. 9) represents the strain field on top of the concrete beam. It can be seen that in the areas where the beam thickness has been increased, the strain decreases. Four of these sections can be easily identified. The dash-dotted line shows the transverse deformation along the beam.

Figure 9. Numerical results from the model, showing strains and displacements.

Figure 10. Close-up of Fig.9 at the composite patch area

A closer view of the repaired area is shown in Fig. 10, for the same conditions. It is important to note that near the tip of composite patch the solid line, representing the strain at the composite surface, has a lower value than the dotted one. That is, near the end of the patch, the strain on top of the composite layer is lower than the strain at the concrete surface.

There is also a sudden reduction in both strains, due to the thicker beam section. The reduction is sharp for the strain at the concrete surface, and smoother for the strain on the composite.

The dash-dotted line shows the shear strain on top of the adhesive layer. Three different peaks are clearly visible. The first one on the left corresponds to the end of the composite layer, while the other two appear each time EI is changed, positive if it is increased and negative if it is decreased (as in the crack element).

Figure 11. *Theoretical and actual values for three sensors as load increases.*

Figure 11 (right) shows the measurements obtained by three sensors placed on the surface of the composite layer close to the center (bottom line), near the end of the layer on top (middle line) and in the interface composite-concrete just below the last sensor (top line), compared with the model prediction when non-linear behaviour of the concrete is included. The straight lines are drawn to enhance the ability to distinguish the second-order effects.

The results obtained through this simple model seem to match the experimental measurements. The trends are similar and the measurements can be explained easily.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The repaired beam shows a mechanical behaviour equal or better than the undamaged beam, demonstrating that this repairing technique may be used in the field of civil engineering, taking advantage of its ease of implementation. Measurements from Bragg gratings match those from strain gauges, and the internal strain field can also be measured.

Strain lag between the surface of the composite patch and the epoxy resin used to bond it can be explained by means of a simple finite element model. A complete mapping of the load transmission was also obtained.

A simple model has been used to explain the measurements in a concrete beam repaired with a composite layer. The model can explain issues like the strain lag at the end of the composite patch, and the non-linear behaviour as the load is increased. Despite the simplicity of the model, results match the expected trends.

The model has also been useful to check that the Bragg grating embedded in the adhesive layer was working properly (hard to check any other way, since no strain gauges were embedded close to it). Once the model has been implemented, more measurement can be carried out to check if the expected behaviour from the model really happens.

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